

ISic0833

The Technitai of Dionysos honour Apollodotos son of Leukios

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2006.04; 2013.09.30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found before 1890 in the area of the in Neapolis

Coordinates

37.075784, 15.275079

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 6

Physical Description

Fragment of a white marble plaque, broken on all sides and worn on the face

Dimensions

Height 6.4 cm

Width 11.4 cm

Depth 3.8 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are notably less regular than ISic0832. Omicron is full; omega is closed; mu has splayed hastae and extended upper strokes; sigma has parallel top and bottom strokes; psi has short upward angled arms; epsilon has nearly equal length bars

Letter heights:

Lines 1-7: 5-7 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. [---]ΩΣΑ[---]
2. [ἀναγράφαι δὲ τὸ ψήφισμα τὸ δεδομέν]ον αὐτοῖς ἐστὴ [λην λιθίνην][---]
3. [ἀναθεῖναι δὲ αὐτοῦ καὶ εἰκόνα ἐ]ν τῷ Μουσείῳ[---]
4. [---][ἐπι]γράφαντας· τὸ κοινὸν [τῶν περὶ τὸν Διόνυσον τεχνιτῶν στεφανοῖ]
5. [---][Ἀ]πολλόδοτον Λευκίῳ [συιὸν][---]
6. [---][ε]ὐεργέτην, κατὰ κα[λοκἀγαθίαν][---]
7. [---]ΟΙΣ[---]

Apparatus

Text after Kaibel in IG 14.13

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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PHI 337021

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